

Some Relations between von Neumann Regular Elements and Quasi-Invertible Elements in Unital Rings

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Abstract

In this paper, the definitions of centrally orthogonal elements, idempotent elements and von Neumann regular elements in unital rings are presented with related examples. Moreover, the concepts of skew corners and quasi-invertible elements with respect to the skew corners are introduced. Finally, we discuss some relations between von Neumann regular elements and quasi-invertible elements in unital rings.

1. Quasi - Invertibility

1. 1. Definition – A nonempty set R is said to be a *ring* if in R there are defined two operations, denoted by $+$ and \cdot respectively, such that for all a, b, c in R :

- (1) $a + b$ is in R
- (2) $a + b = b + a$
- (3) $(a+b) + c = a + (b+c)$
- (4) There is an element 0 in R such that $a + 0 = a$ for every a in R .
- (5) There exists an element $-a$ in R such that $a + (-a) = 0$ for every a in R .
- (6) $a \cdot b$ is in R .
- (7) $a \cdot (b \cdot c) = (a \cdot b) \cdot c$
- (8) $a \cdot (b+c) = a \cdot b + a \cdot c$ and $(b+c) \cdot a = b \cdot a + c \cdot a$

1. 2. Definition - A ring with multiplicative identity is called a unital ring. The multiplicative identity is generally denoted by 1 .

1. 3. Definition An invertible element or a unit in unital ring R is an $uv = vu = 1$. The set of invertible element are denoted by R^{-1} .

1. 4. Definition The two elements x and y in R are *centrally orthogonal* in symbols $x \perp y$ if $xRy = 0$. and $yRx = 0$.

1. 5. Example. zero '0' is centrally orthogonal elements in ring of real numbers.

Here and else where we use R for unital ring.

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1. 6. Definition An element of a ring R , say x is said to be **idempotent** if $x^2 = x$.

1. 7. Example. The idempotent elements are 0 and 1 in ring of real numbers.

1. 8. Definition Let p, q be idempotents in R . The subsets of the form $p R q$ are called **skew corners**.

1. 9. Example. Consider Two idempotents elements are 0 and 1 in R .

So zero ring and R ring are skew corners of ring R .

1. 10. Definition Let p and q be idempotents in a ring R such that the skew corner $p R q \neq 0$. We say that an element x in $p R q$ is **quasi-invertible** with respect to skew corner, if there exist elements a, b in $q R p$ such that $(p-xa) \perp (q-bx)$ and write $x \in (p R q)_q^{-1}$.

The set of quasi-invertible elements in R will be denoted by R_q^{-1}

1. 11. Definition For each subset A of a unital ring R we define $Cl(A)$ to be the set of elements a in R such that $xa + b = I$, for some elements x and b in R there is an element y in R such that $a + yb \in A$.

1. 12. Definition The ring R is said to be a **B-ring**, if for every a, b and x in R such that $xa + b = I$, there is y in R such that $a + yb \in R^{-1}$.

1. 13. Definition We say that R is a **QB - ring**, with respect to quasi-invertible elements if $Cl(R_q^{-1}) = R$.

1. 14. Definition An element a in a ring R is **von Neumann regular** if $a = axa$ for some x in R . In that case we say that x is a partial inverse for a .

The set of von Neumann regular elements in R will be denoted by R^r .

1. 15. Example.

Zero is von Neumann regular element in the rings of real numbers.

1. 16. Definition If a and b are von Neumann regular elements in R we say that **b extends a** if $a = axb = bxa = axa$ for some x in R .

We write it by $a \leq b$.

1. 17. Example. Let R be the ring of real numbers.

Take $a = 0, b = 1, 0 = 0x1 = 1x0 = 1x0 = 0x0 = 0$.

Thus $0 \leq 1$.

2. Relations

If a and b are von Neumann regular elements in R , a b and x is partial inverse for a and a as its partial inverse, y is a partial inverse for b , with b as its partial inverse, then we have the following simple relations:

$$ax = bx, xa = xb$$

$$a = ayb = bya$$

$$a = bxb = aya$$

We now have all the pieces required to prove our ambition some relations between von Neumann regular elements and quasi-invertible elements in ring R .

Proposition – 1. The relation \leq defined above on the set R^r of von Neumann regular elements in a ring R is a partial order on R^r .

Proof:

It is obvious that \leq is reflexive. Suppose that $a \leq b$ and $b \leq a$. Then $aR = bR$. Hence $a=b$.

Therefore the relation \leq is antisymmetric. Let $a \leq b$ and $b \leq c$ then we may assume that a and b have partial inverses x and y respectively. Now put $x' = yay$, then we have $ax'a = a$, $x'ax' = x'$, $x' = x'ay = yax'$.

We replace x with x' , we obtain.

$$axa = x \text{ and } x = xay = yax = xax$$

It follows that $x \leq y$. Since $b \leq c$ and y is partial inverse for b , we have $by = cy$ by (i). The $cxa = c(yax)a = (cy)(axa) = (by)a = a$.

Similar, $axc = a$, so $a \leq c$. Therefore the relation \leq is transitive. Thus the relation \leq is partial order on R^r .

Proposition – 2. Each element in R_q^{-1} is maximal in R^r with respect to the ordering \leq .

Proof:

If $u \in R_q^{-1}$ and $u \leq a$ for some a in R^r , then

$$u = uvu = avu = uva \text{ for some } v \text{ in } R.$$

Then v is a quasi – inverse for u .

$$\text{In particular } a = a - (I - uv) a (I - vu) = uva + avu - uvavu = u + u - uvu = u$$

Theorem – 1. Let a be a von Neumann regular element in a ring R . If $a \in Cl(R_q^{-1})$, the $a \leq u$ for some u in (R_q^{-1}) .

Proof:

Let a be a von Neumann regular element in a unital ring R . By assumption $a = axa$ and $x = xax$ for some x in R . Define the idempotents $p = I - ax$ and $q = I - xa$, where $pa = aq = 0$. Then, $xa + q = I$ and since $a \in Cl(R_q^{-1})$ this means that $a + pyq \in R_q^{-1}$ for some y in R .

If we now define $u = a + pyq$ then it follows from proposition 2 that $a \leq u$.

From the above theorem, we get the following results.

- (1) In a unital *QB-ring* R , every von Neumann regular element extends to a quasi-invertible element.
- (2) In a unital *QB-ring* R , an element in R' is maximal with respect to the order \leq if and only if it belongs to R_q^{-1} .

Corollary 1.1 . In a unital *QB-ring* R , every von Neumann regular element extends to a quasi-invertible element.

Proof:

Assume that a is von Neumann regular element in R . Since R is a *QB-ring*, we have $a \in R = Cl(R_q^{-1})$. Therefore, by above theorem we obtain $a \leq u$ for some $u \in R_q^{-1}$.

Corollary 1.2 . In a unital *QB-ring* R , an element in R' is maximal with respect to the order \leq if and only if it belongs to R_q^{-1} .

Proof:

In view of proposition 2 we need only consider an element a in R' which is maximally extended, and prove that $a \in R_q^{-1}$. But that can be seen easily from corollary 1.1.

Conclusion

I hope that this paper will be useful to those who are studying in Ring Theory.

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